

Representation of Horses in Mainstream Animation, and How it Affects Their Welfare

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BA Animation (Hons), 2026

FSFM6008 Dissertation

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1. Introduction

This essay aims to analyse the representation of horses in mainstream animation compared to Anna Sewell's groundbreaking novel, *Black Beauty* (1877), how common tropes and stereotypes reinforce public perception by normalising harmful practices, and impact the welfare of equines in real life. A variety of titles will be compared and contrasted while providing cultural, behavioral, statistical and systematic contexts.

The main titles used will be *Spirit: Stallion of the Cimarron* (2002), *Silver Spoon* (2013), *Centaurworld* (2021), *Umamasume: Pretty Derby* (2021). They will be compared to common tropes and stereotypes found in a variety of mainstream animated movies and TV shows, included but not limited to films by Walt Disney, Dreamworks, and shows from Netflix.

2. Why This Matters

Throughout history, horses have broadened our horizons, sparked our imagination, and provided us with service, companionship, and food. Since their domestication about 5,000 years ago, horses have played an indispensable role in the evolution of human civilisation. (Taylor, 2024:xvi). Not only that, the first-ever moving picture was *The Horse in Motion*, a sequence of images capturing a horse's gallop using a tripwire to trigger twelve consecutive cameras (Papacosta, 2018). Horses were, therefore, directly responsible for the birth of animation and cinema.

Despite all they have done for us, the partnership between horse and man has always been one-sided, based on coercion and exploitation (Hribal, 2010). More often than not, they were overworked; and at the end of their life they were unceremoniously killed (Barnett, 2006). The use of horses and other working animals was usually taken for granted through necessitation, trivialisation and cultural conditioning.

Even in the modern equestrian industry, horse welfare is far from optimal. Horses are still pushed to their mental and biomechanical limits for human entertainment. The training and upkeep of horses is archaic and outdated. Thousands of horses are bred every year for sport, with a majority of them ending up neglected, starved, mistreated, and shipped to slaughter (Barnett, 2006). According to the RSPCA Horse Crisis Report 2025, human factors such as beliefs and attitudes towards horses is one of the biggest contributors to their welfare.

"Horses are often seen as commodities; a resource to make money from by breeding, selling or slaughter, or as a tool to use to achieve personal sporting goals. A lack of consideration of their sentience denies that they have feelings and interests of their own, and results in inappropriate treatment." (RSPCA, 2025).

It is indisputable that representation of a subject is not a reflection of reality, but a construction of meaning that "influence[s] our conduct and consequently ha[s] real, practical effects" (Hall *et al.*, 2013). Horses have always held a special place in human imagination, with a majority of cave paintings and prehistoric sculptures featuring horses millennia before they were ridden (*Chevaux du Monde*,

2025). The prevalence of horses in media such as paintings, sculptures, literature, and moving images across all cultures and all human history is consistent with this fascination.

However, horses are overwhelmingly often depicted submitting to human will in some way, i.e. being ridden, driven, or trained. Their eyes are wide, ears pinned, tail swishing, necks either overly round and low or arched and high. Their facial muscles are tense, and mouths are often open and foaming, which is a sign of pain and damage caused by forceful or prolonged pressure on the bit in their mouth (Christensen, 2024). Their riders or drivers often wield whips or similar devices to establish dominance. Even in art without humans or riders, these traits find themselves on the horse subjects, evidencing their normalisation.

Fig. 1 *Napoleon Crossing the Alps*, painting by Jacques-Louis David (1801)

These depictions are harmful, and parallel well-documented cases in which domestic violence, corporal punishment, and colonial dominance have been culturally justified and rendered invisible through aestheticisation and repetition in media (Bourdieu, 1991; Stark, 2007; Gershoff & Grogan-Kaylor, 2016; Said, 1997; cited by ChatGPT, 2026a).

In animation, *Cinderella* (1950) contains an example of this enculturation. Very early in the film, we see Cinderella with her father. She is shown petting a non-anthromorphised grey horse – presumably young Major – and her father is seen smiling down at her. While the scene is one of nostalgia and familial love, the father holds a horse-whip in his hands. Despite plenty of evidence that whips cause pain, hinder performance, and do not increase safety in most cases, they are considered a “necessary aid for horsemanship” (Jones *et al.*, 2015). Thus, the presence of a whip in an otherwise heartwarming scene desensitises the audience to its presence and implied use.

Fig. 2 *Cinderella's Father Holding a Whip* (1950)

Therefore, the way horses are seen and shown in media must change significantly if the mainstream attitude towards them – and therefore their welfare – is to improve.

3. Exclusions

There are certain representations of animated horses that are excluded from this essay, as they are judged too far removed from real horses to have any significant impact on their welfare or reputation.

3.1 *The Last Unicorn* (1982)

Representations of unicorns are typically excluded by this essay. Traditionally, they resembled goats, bovines, or donkeys instead of horses in folklore, and are generally considered a completely different animal even when they do resemble horses. No folklore or story involves riding a unicorn - only capturing or slaying them. Unicorns also hold an entirely different set of symbols than horses do.

In *The Last Unicorn* (1982), for example, there was no indication that unicorns are comparable to or can be treated like horses. Even when the Unicorn is captured by a witch called Mommy Fortuna, the story presents it as akin to capturing a rare magical creature instead of a horse.

The film also features plenty of ordinary horses who serve as nothing more than transport, and the presence of a talking unicorn journeying among humans does not change the way the characters or audience see them.

3.2 *My Little Pony: Friendship is Magic* (2010)

Even though *My Little Pony: Friendship Is Magic* (2010) is a popular mainstream animated show that features a multitude of equines both real and mythical, they are visually and narratively so far removed

from their origins that they only vaguely resemble horses. Humans are seemingly nonexistent in this story, and the characters live in societies and cultures similar to those of humans, building cities, institutions, governments, and owning non-equine critters as their pets.

My Little Pony fans barely consider these pastel characters as their real-life counterparts. In a popular poll, 39% of participants answered "No" when asked whether they liked real-life horses. Despite the availability of options "I didn't, but I do now" and "Other" (*Equestria Daily*, 2011), only 36% answered "Yes". Several participants stated that they like the ponies in *My Little Pony: Friendship Is Magic* precisely due to their lack of visual and behavioural resemblance to real-life horses.

These results can be summed up as follows:

"Although the show stars horses and employs horse-related paraphernalia to create an immersive environment, it does not aim to be a true representation of the horse experience, and nor do its fans want it that way." (Robertson, 2013)

As a result, it is highly unlikely that *My Little Pony: Friendship Is Magic* would have any impact on the welfare of real-life horses.

4. Black Beauty (1877)

Anna Sewell's only novel, *Black Beauty* (1877), was a first-of-its-kind story that generated worldwide empathy for the widely-exploited working horses at that time. Known as "The autobiography of a horse", it follows the first-person narration of Black Beauty – a black Thoroughbred horse born in Victorian England – as he goes through several homes and masters whose treatment of him ranges between kindness, ignorance, and cruelty.

Though it is a book, *Black Beauty* serves as a great benchmark for horse representation due to the profound impact it had – and continues to have – for the welfare of horses and animals at large. The novel's description of the pain inflicted by bearing reins – equipment used to force horses' heads up for fashion purposes – led to their abolition (Dorré 2002: 157–78). Within two years of its release, one million copies of the novel were in circulation in the USA, and even now it is considered "the most influential anti-cruelty novel of all time" (Unti, 1998).

4.1 Cooperative Horse Narrative

Despite that, it contains and reinforces the most pervasive and deep-rooted trope found within horse stories - the Cooperative Horse Narrative (Friedman, 2025a). From his mother's advice to always "keep up his good name" no matter how he is treated by humans, to Black Beauty's endless tolerance and willingness to serve his masters leading to his ultimately happy ending, to the punishments endured by another horse – Ginger – simply for resisting cruelty – it is clear that the story rewards cooperation towards human owners no matter how cruel they may be.

Found even in stories containing horses as their protagonists, this trope is a result of the deeply-rooted anthropocentric mentality that the lives and minds of animals revolve around the service and happiness of their human partners. It serves to "legitimise a narrative in which horses are eager to be at the service of humans (human-oriented anthropomorphism) and ... naturalise asymmetries of power" (Friedman, 2025a). This trope is comparable to the Happiness in Slavery trope, which played a part in the normalisation of slavery.

In animation, this trope presents itself in a wide variety of ways, depending on the level of anthropomorphism a horse character exhibits.

5. Anthropomorphism – Objectification of Horses in Disney

Though this is a spectrum, horses are generally depicted as either realistic, expressionless, and utilitarian (Objectified), or caricatured and expressive (Anthropomorphised). As *Walt Disney Animation Studios* (WDAS) animated films take place in primarily medieval settings, it is ideal for studying the representation of horses along this spectrum.

5.1 Objectified Horses

In most animated films featuring them, horses exist as nothing more than background props alluding to the historic realism of the settings. They are often hidden in shadows, unmoving, identical, nameless, genderless, and without any personality features. Their eyes are 'realistic' – either solid-coloured with no sclera, or covered with blinkers and hidden entirely. They are a metaphorically objectified depiction of a living animal.

Fig. 3 *Non-Anthropomorphised Horse Waiting in the Rain, Lady and the Tramp* (1955)

Through frequent objectification, WDAS films contain and promote a certain speciesism against horses. Even though horses are the "second most commonly depicted species across all of the fifty-six WDAS films" (Stanton, 2021:100), they are rarely anthropomorphised in the way other WDAS mammals such as dogs, cats, and wild animals are. Even in films like *Snow White* (1937), *Lady and the*

Tramp (1955), *The Little Mermaid* (1989), and *Princess and the Frog* (2009), which feature plenty of anthropomorphised animals, horses remain mute beasts of burden to be used and not empathised with. Froufrou from *Aristocats* (1979) is a notable exception to this.

Often, these horses' lack of characterisation makes it okay for them to be hurt. When horses across all forms of animation are depicted being urged from a stop, it is a common sight for them to be whipped, slapped or physically struck in some way first, normalising the harsh treatment of horses.

In the climax of *Lady and the Tramp* (1955), an anthropomorphised bloodhound named Trusty chases the dog-catcher's horse-drawn wagon to rescue Tramp. Catching up, he intentionally frightens the silhouetted horses, leading to a collision which seriously injures him. While Trusty is shown lying lifelessly in the street and mourned by the other dogs, the narrative encourages no sympathy for the non-anthropomorphised horses he startled, there is no reflection for their injuries, and they are never shown again (Stanton, 2021:114). This implied hierarchy – between the anthropomorphised and not – could result in reducing empathy for real-life animals, as they do not behave like Disneyfied animals.

Though the number of anthropomorphised horses has increased in WDAS films, objectification of horses takes place even in works as recent as *Encanto* (2021). In a scene at the end of the movie, Bruno appears astride a random bay horse to find Mirabelle and Alma after the movie's emotional conclusion. They all mount this horse as Bruno asks where they are going. Mirabelle dramatically replies "Home," before kicking the horse's sides and causing it to gallop back towards the town. The horse jumps over a log on the way, and stops once arrived.

Much like those from past WDAS films, this horse's eyes, form, and movements are photorealistic, unlike other anthropomorphised animals in the film such as jaguars, capybaras, toucans, and even donkeys. Its face is hidden and out of view as much as possible, with the camera choosing to focus on its body where its utility lies. When its face and eyes are visible, the camera chooses to blur them out of focus to keep the audience's attention on the characters.

Fig. 4 Objectified Horse in *Encanto* (2021)

Other Disney movies featuring more anthropomorphised horses, such as *Beauty and the Beast* (1991) and *Frozen* (2013), did not utilise such measures, even during high-stakes scenes which prioritised the human characters.

Along with the practice of kicking horses, which is conditioned as acceptable due to a protagonist doing it, this scene also normalises double/triple riding on horses. It is not common knowledge that horses are living beings with a limited amount of weight they can carry safely – up to 15-20% of their own body weight (Challinor, 2021). Horses weigh 500 kilograms on average, making the average carrying capacity 100kg - and three adult humans far surpasses this.

Therefore, despite improvements, Disney's speciesism towards horses and their objectification of them is not a relic of a bygone era.

5.2 Anthropomorphised Horses

Later WDAS movies saw an increase in the frequency of anthropomorphised horses, some of whom – particularly Maximus from *Tangled* (2010) – have become fan favourites. Anthropomorphised horses are characterised as loyal, brave, and cooperative, evoking the nature of oversized dogs. Despite their increased expressivity, most of these horses are mute.

Anthropomorphism of animals can have both positive and detrimental effects. Enhancing naturally occurring humanlike traits in animals can make them more relatable to the audience and create empathy for them, which can lead to higher conservation efforts in cases like Smokey the Bear (Russel, 2014). On the other hand, it can harm public perception of animals and justify their mistreatment, such as anthropomorphised stories of foxes being used to promote foxhunting (Fernandez, 2024).

Horses are often similarly anthropomorphised in real life, in order to justify their mistreatment. Being prey animals, horses are designed to flee from perceived danger and discomfort. However, due to widespread ignorance of horse behaviour, their natural fight-or-flight or pain-avoidance behaviours are often characterised as defiance, domination, or 'sassiness' by their caretakers, and are unhelpfully countered with punishment.

In animation, horses are typically anthropomorphised in line with the cooperative horse narrative. Their behaviour and motivations revolve around their human partner, even when the human partner is absent. When not in service, they are seen all alone, even though horses are social animals and form lifelong bonds with their herd members (Argent, 2012). Animated horses never seem to tire and can gallop for days, even though real horses can only gallop flat-out for half a mile to a few miles at a time. They are far more vocal than real horses, in order to be more expressive.

An interesting trend across a majority of anthropomorphised horses, in both Eastern and Western animation, is the omission or censorship of the metallic bit. Whether or not the horse talks does not seem to effect this. Moreover, horses belonging to villains – even when anthropomorphised – are shown with bits, and are roughly ridden, more often than those owned by protagonists.

Fig. 5 *Phillipe and Gaston's Horse from Beauty and the Beast (1991)*

Considering that bits are still widely-used and even mandatory in most modern equestrian sports despite the oral damage they cause (Doherty *et al.*, 2017), this trend implies an awareness that bits should not be normalised in children's media.

5.3 Middle Ground

These WDAS horses walk the line between the extremes of objectification and over-anthropomorphism. Though their horse-like behaviour and instincts are sometimes an inconvenience to the human characters, the horses are not punished for it, neither by a character nor by the narrative.

Phillipe from *Beauty and the Beast* (1991) is an example. He is a mute, palomino-coloured draft horse with sturdy shape language, and is characterised as reliable but cautious. When he and Maurice (Belle's father) are lost in the woods, he senses danger in Maurice's chosen path and tries to turn the other way. This is an accurate representation of horses' antipredatory reflexes and heightened senses as prey animals, giving them the ability to sense danger before their human partners (Bercy *et al.*, 2025).

Though not with as much screentime, *Frozen* (2013) also features anthropomorphised ridden horses who are similar to Phillippe.

6. Untamable Steeds and Horse Whisperers

In *Frozen 2* (2021), Elsa fights a horse-shaped water spirit called "the Nokk" – based on Nokken in Scandanavian mythology (Nordvig, 2025). It tries to drown her and drag her across the water, but she successfully tames it by putting an ice bridle on it and riding it until it stops bucking. Inspirational music plays as Elsa pets its neck and it whinnies at her happily, indicating that it is tame, and follows her every command henceforth.

Fig. 6 *Elsa Taming the Nokk*, (2021)

This is an example of the widely used Untamable Steed trope, in which a character demonstrates their courage, tenacity, and sometimes empathy by submitting a rebellious horse (or other steed) to their will. It uses aestheticised dominance, using slow motion shots and swelling music to frame cruelty as strength (ChatGPT, 2026a). The horse is typically characterised as dangerous, naughty, skittish, or as 'testing the chosen one', and becomes docile and friendly upon taming.

In reality, a bucking horse is simply displaying the fight-or-flight instincts of a prey animal. Their taming or breaking-in is achieved with flooding – exposing an individual to intense anxiety-inducing stimulus without any means of escape – leading to exhaustion and learned helplessness (Seligmen, 1972). Horses trained this way often revert back to their 'disobedient' instincts once their energy is recovered, and require repetition over a period of time before they can be considered "Fully broke".

The polar opposite of this trope is the equally popular Horse Whisperer or Perfect Match narrative, which involves an inexperienced, usually-female rider forming unbreakable bonds with a wild or troublesome horse in an extremely short amount of time. This trope is omnipresent in the Horse Girl genre of fiction, and is prevalent across film, TV, and literature. *Spirit Untamed* (2021) is an animated example.

Fig. 7 *Romanticised Depiction of Horse Ownership* (2021)

Though much kinder than the trope previously mentioned, this trope has its own dangers. The 'Disney effect' is a repeatedly-observed phenomenon in which depictions of animals in film "strongly influence the species and breeds that people subsequently choose as pets" (Stanton, 2021:86). Despite the name, it is not exclusive to Disney or even animation. An example of this is the increased demand for Dalmatians after the release of *One Hundred and One Dalmatians* (1961). When owners learnt that Dalmatians were a high-energy breed, not matching their leisurely depiction in the film, many of them were given away to shelters. (Stanton, 2021:86)

Horse Whisperer stories overly romanticise the experience of horse ownership and create unrealistic fantasies in the minds of children – a phenomenon dubbed 'The Pony Phase'. Many child audiences are compelled to buy a pony or horse, and soon realise that caring for horses requires a lot of time, effort, patience and money. This usually ends with the horse being resold or sent to a shelter, contributing to the widespread abandonment and neglect of horses (RSPCA, 2025).

7. Highlighted Examples

The following are some examples of media that break the mold when it comes to representing the horse experience. Part of this is due to the fact that they all feature horses as important to their story - if not as the protagonists. However, they are not flawless, and their limitations will be highlighted along with their strengths.

7.1 Spirit: Stallion of the Cimarron (2002)

Created by DreamWorks Pictures, this is one of the first ever mainstream animated films starring a non-mythological horse as its central protagonist. It follows a wild Kiger mustang stallion in the old Western frontier. The horses in this film don't speak, although Spirit – played by Matt Damon – occasionally narrates his thoughts non-diegetically to the audience. The film shows the contrast between Spirit's life in the wild with his herd, the colonising US Army, and the Lakota people who respect nature.

It tactfully and accurately represents the harsh training and equipment used in the breaking of horses in the past, many of which are still prevalent today. In the film, Spirit endures common experiences such as being lassoed, confined, branded (the practice of searing a symbol of ownership into the skin using hot iron), exhausted, spurred, and 'broken' (outdated methods of training a horse to accept a saddle and rider). When Little Creek – the Lakota character – removes the bit in Spirit's mouth, he chews and stretches his jaw, indicating the soreness it caused. There are many similar small moments that attempt to de-normalise the exploitation of horses.

The fully broken military horses being marched at camp, who would typically be objectified or naturalised, are presented front and center as Spirit watches their coordinated steps in horror. When Spirit whinnies at them questioningly, one of the horses stops to reply, and is immediately spurred by his rider for breaking the formation. Using filmmaking techniques, this scene presents a very common sight – marching horses – in an entirely new light. These background horses also react to Spirit's resistance to training – laughing when he succeeds, and mourning when he fails.

Fig. 8 *Spirit Looking At His Future* (2002)

Spirit: The Stallion of the Cimarron also directly opposes the Cooperative Horse narrative, as Spirit is narratively rewarded for his resistance towards the US Army's harsh training. However, the story forces Spirit to cooperate with his more sympathetic captor, Little Creek, in order to "earn" his freedom. Only after letting the Lakota ride him so they can escape from the colonialists' pursuit, is Spirit granted his freedom and titular name by Little Creek. Therefore, despite the radical subversion, the narrative still implicitly reinforces the cooperative horse narrative. (Friedman, 2025b)

Though the increased awareness is hard to measure, this film had a positive impact on the welfare of wild mustang populations in the USA. Spirit's real-life model of the same name, aged 31 at the time of writing, still lives at the Return to Freedom wild horse sanctuary and acts as an ambassador for wild horses. He continues to attract fans of the film and educate the public about the protection of American mustangs.

7.1.1 Symbolic Reduction of Horses

Due to their prevalence in so many eras, cultures, and art forms, horses have come to symbolise a multitude of concepts ranging from natural forces such as oceans, wilderness and the sun, to abstract values such as freedom, power and status (Wikipedia, 2026). Different breeds, colours, genders, and traits of horses each carry their own set of symbols. This overuse of horses in usually-unrelated symbolism can

lead to their symbolic reduction – flattening their individual, lived experience beyond what they represent.

Animation does this too. In *Animal Farm* (1954), Boxer the workhorse serves as an allegory for the Russian working class (Wermelin, 2017). In *Bojack Horseman* (2014), the titular character acts and is treated as a post-fame middle-aged man, with the head of a horse serving as nothing more than a parallel to their obsolescence in modern society (De Koster, 2018).

In *Spirit: Stallion of the Cimarron*, both the horse's internal monologue and the storyline draw direct parallels between the US Army's treatment of wild horses and the colonisation of Native Americans. Mustangs are considered a symbol of patriotism in North America (Horton, 2017). This story can therefore be considered symbolic or allegorical of identity, freedom, and anti-colonial resistance.

7.2 Silver Spoon (2013)

Written by Hiromu Arakawa, *Silver Spoon* (2013) is a slice-of-life about Yuugo Hachiken, a city high-schooler who joins an agriculture school to escape his overbearing parents. It tells an emotionally rich and thought-provoking story, exploring the sometimes harsh nature of the agricultural industry and how it affects the people and animals within it. It encourages the audience to be appreciative of farm life, animals, and where food comes from.

Silver Spoon does not try to anthropomorphise any of its animal characters, presenting them 'as is' to best of its abilities without erasing their sentience, and each species gets a chance to shine through cultural misunderstandings.

Horses feature frequently in *Silver Spoon*, as Hachiken is persuaded to join the school's Equestrian Club by his classmate Aki, whose uncle owns a horse farm. Though he knows nothing about horses, he soon learns to appreciate them despite their challenging maintenance – as the show does not downplay the amount of work it takes to care for horses. He learns that despite their intimidating size, horses are shy and sensitive animals who value their herd, and that they respect those who treat them with kindness.

Maron, Hachiken's usual ride, is drawn in an intentionally ugly artstyle to push forward the show's recurring theme of not judging a book by its cover. Though Maron is a prideful and sometimes 'quirky' horse, he "takes his job seriously" (*Silver Spoon: Season 1, Episode 2*, 2013) and is never blamed or villainised for his riders' mistakes or inexperience.

Fig. 9 Horses: Maron and Mikage Homare (2013)

Episode 3 is the most horse-centric one, as Aki takes Hachiken to a Ban'ei (sled-pulling) race that her uncle's horse is participating in. After the race, Hachiken learns and grapples with the fact that under-performing horses are slaughtered, and their effort is not rewarded. He is later told that being a vet sometimes means knowing when to kill, because all animals cannot be saved. At the end of the episode, they come across the funeral procession of a horse who collapsed mid-race. They pay their respects as Aki's uncle says:

"We make our living with horses, so we'd like to give them all a proper funeral, but business is tough. Just because of the life they were born into, they're stuck in a life-or-death existence ... decided upon a person's single whim. If we ever come to completely understand how a horse feels, we might go crazy." (*Silver Spoon: Season 1, Episode 3*, 2013)

That said, *Silver Spoon* is not a show about animal advocacy or systemic change. Animals are slaughtered on-screen multiple times, even if solemnly. Though Hachiken questions the harsh lives of agrarian animals and farmers, the show and its characters have a very 'it is what it is' attitude towards factors out of their control. Instead, the show encourages personal responsibility and coming to one's own conclusions.

Silver Spoon is not associated with any recorded improvement in animal welfare or horse welfare, but it increased tourism in Hokkaido (Mason, 2016), where fans could gain a deeper awareness about farm life, animals and Ban'ei races. It inspired several fans to pursue agricultural careers, some of which involve animal welfare.

7.3 Centaurworld (2021)

Centaurworld (2021) is an animated comedy-drama musical from Netflix Animation, and stars a horse protagonist (simply called "Horse") who gets transported from her medieval war-torn setting into a colourful world of singing centaurs of all species, shapes and sizes. She longs to get back to her only liv-

ing family – her rider (simply known as "Rider") – and goes through a character arc of change and self-acceptance.

At the beginning of the show, Horse is similar to Phillipe from *Beauty and the Beast* (1991) in terms of being mute and exhibiting realistic horse behaviour, such as getting spooked by burning cinders. Aside from having front-facing expressive eyes, her form and movements are similar to real horses.

Fig. 10 *Horse in Episode 1, Centaurworld* (2021)

Horse's newfound anthropomorphism – her ability to talk and anthropomorphised movements – is a direct effect of her being transported to Centaurworld – and she expresses her surprise for the same: "Did I just speak words? With my mouth?" and "I guess I can do math now" (*Centaurworld: Season 1, Episode 1*, 2021). This change being an in-universe phenomenon may help the audience disassociate Horse's increasingly un-horse-like behaviour from that of real horses.

The show directly addresses modern horse welfare using comedy, when Horse is forced to participate in a talent show to return home. Zulus, a perfectionist tasked with coaching Horse, slaps her to make a point. The video pauses and a comedic disclaimer flashes: "*PLEASE DO NOT SLAP HORSES" (*Centaurworld: Season 1, Episode 7*, 2021). This happens a few more times during the conversation, with the text changing each time.

Fig. 11 *Please Do Not Slap Horses* (2021)

Centaurworld is a slapstick, which is "a type of physical comedy characterised by broad humour, absurd situations and vigorous, usually violent action" (Peacock, 2014) so characters interacting in this way is unlikely to encourage mistreatment of real horses. In contrast, the show also regularly uses fantastical elements and comedy to challenge psychological and political themes, such as trauma, identity, self-harm/suicide, war, and aristocratic privilege (Pass, 2025). Considering that Horse is also in a similar position as a non-consenting performing horse in real life – it would not be a leap to assume that this scene was created to make a statement towards the equine industry.

As aforementioned, slapping or otherwise using physical force on horses is very common in both media and in real life. Aggressive or avoidant behaviour, which more often than not indicates a health or welfare concern, is interpreted as attitude, disobedience or dominance, and thus countered with punishment.

From a study interviewing equestrians about horse welfare, this response perfectly encapsulates this mentality:

"He [*the horse*] snoots. You know, ears back and ... flares his nostrils at everybody. But yet, there's no reason. Like he's never been... oh, he'll get a whack if he's naughty, but he's never been mistreated. ... hasn't been tied or flogged or dropped ... Everyone's against me type attitude [*from the horse*]." (Anonymous, 2023; cited in Luke *et al.*, 2023).

Centaurworld, with its realistic horse animation, is very appealing to equestrians and other horse lovers. The fact that this splash text has found its way onto a wide variety of unofficial merchandise such

as stickers, t-shirts, and badges says something about this moment resonating with the audience and potentially making a difference in the welfare of real horses.

7.3.1 War Horses

There are things to be said about the show's use of toilet humour potentially detrimenting the attitude towards equines, Horse's relationship with Rider veering into the Cooperative Horse Narrative, and other common anthropomorphism problems. However, there is another common trope found across many depictions of horses, including *Centaurworld*, that remains to be addressed: the archetypal war horse.

Since a lot of mainstream depictions of horses – especially animated – take place in medieval or medieval fantasy times during which horses were used for war, they are often depicted as chivalrous, brave, and loyal to both their human teammates and abstract concepts such as nations. This causes a romanticised or oversimplified impression of the use of horses and other animals in war.

The reality is that the horse's nature as a prey animal means that their instinct is to flee from danger, and they have no contextual understanding of heroism, patriotism, and sacrifice (Nocella *et al.*, 2023:27). Even if they survived the overcrowding, overwork, harsh treatment, disease, starvation and combat situations they had to face, only one in a million war horses were safely return home in the World Wars, while the rest of the survivors were slaughtered to feed the returning soldiers (Nocella *et al.*, 2023:27).

The most famous example of this trope is *War Horse* (2011), but it is found in several WDAS films such as *Sleeping Beauty* (1959), *The Hunchback of Notre-Dame* (1996), *Mulan* (1998) and *Tangled* (2010), all of which feature horses who exhibit traits similar to soldiers – such as bravery, honour, and patriotism. Thus, the war horse narrative is another example of the symbolic reduction of horses.

Both horses in *Centaurworld* - Horse and Becky Apples - are characterised as bold, fearless, hardened warriors who charge into danger and are eager to kill, with Horse singing in the second episode: "I never feared the drums of war, I crushed the skulls and I want more" (*Centaurworld: Season 1, Episode 2*, 2021). There are other moments in the show, which naturalise horses in war and portray them with the same agency as a human soldier, such as the following statement by Horse:

"You think anybody sang me a song when it was time for war in my world? No, they put a saddle on me, strapped a feed bag around my head and threw me into the chaos. And guess what? I was fine [...] Because we horses – we *get it*." (*Centaurworld: Season 2, Episode 1*, 2021)

7.3.2 You're Just a Horse – A Missed Opportunity

Centaurworld, within its final episodes, presents the viewer with a rare addressal of speciesism and anthropocentrism within the story, but fails to resolve or explore it in a meaningful way.

All centaurs are half-animal (with the occasional plant) with Horse being full animal. A flashback in the final episode reveals that, before their worlds were separated, centaurs were subservient to and looked down upon by humans. The show's antagonist and only other talking animal – The Nowhere King or The Elk – was once part of a centaur called Elktaur who yearned to be "Taken seriously" by humans (illustrated through a man teasing his dog with a stick for his amusement). All of Elktaur's drastic actions – such as chopping off his antlers, separating himself from his beast half, and inflicting great suffering upon the Elk – can be considered a consequence of human prejudice towards centaurs, and by extension animals.

In the same episode, Horse tries to explain to her Rider that to kill The Nowhere King, they would have to kill his other half – their General. Rider argues, disbelieving and unwilling to kill her mentor. When Horse pleads Rider to trust her, she simply states: "How could you possibly know what to do? You're just a horse" (*Centaurworld: Season 2, Episode 8*, 2021), which both hurts Horse and prolongs their eventual victory. Rider's display of speciesism is a surprising moment as Horse and Rider have been characterised as each other's "closest family", lifelong comrades, and have spent most of the show's duration trying to find each other.

But this conflict is entirely resolved when Rider - betrayed and wounded by the General - apologises by saying "You were never just a horse, you are my best friend". Elktaur's conflict is similarly trivialised, and humanity's past prejudice towards centaurs is never addressed in the present, leaving the audience to assume that both worlds returned to living in harmony.

Though the show uses speciesism in the story to push forward its core themes of identity and self-acceptance, it fails to address or problemise the demonstrated speciesism itself, normalising it and having a potentially negative affect on animal/horse welfare.

7.4 Umamasume: Pretty Derby (2021)

Out of all other examples, the unexpected multimedia franchise *Umamasume: Pretty Derby* (2021) created by Cygames has had the biggest measurable impact on the welfare of horses in real life. Originally announced as a mobile Gacha game, it expanded to include a manga, anime series, and multiple live concerts.

It is primarily a sports simulator game set in an alternate world, where horses are replaced with *Umamasume* - anime girls with the ears, tails, and capabilities of horses, who seek to gain fame by competing in organised races similar to track events or horse races. It uses the power of animation, anthropomorphism, and storytelling in a highly unexpected way, as each of these characters are named after real-life legendary Japanese racehorses, with stories adapted from their careers, running styles, rivalries, and personalities (*Memoroar*, 2025).

Fig. 12 *Umamusume: Pretty Derby Game Cover* (2021)

This has led the global anime and gacha communities to be invested in the lives and careers of the racehorses that inspired these beloved characters. Dedicated fans have flown to Japan to visit the characters' namesakes, donated thousands of kilograms of ryegrass to Haru Urara, a racehorse with record-holding losses (Zotomayor, 2025), and fundraised for the retirement homes of legendary racehorses Meisho Doto and Transcend (Busby, 2025). In a particularly optimistic incident, *Umamusume* fans across social media also came together to save a Brazilian retired racehorse named Risk, who was destined for slaughter (Glaze, 2025).

7.4.1 Dark Side of the Horseracing Industry

Unfortunately, on the other hand, this franchise depends on, benefits, and leads to the glorification of an industry that is responsible for both large-scale exploitation of horses and the upholding of narratives that make horse abuse publicly acceptable.

Though stakeholders often say racehorses are "treated like kings" outside their work hours, racehorses are generally deprived of the 'Three Fs' of horse welfare, which stand for "Friends, Forage, and Freedom" (RSPCA, 2025). This causes racehorses to have a much higher rate of repetitive stress behaviours and gastric ulcers than other equine populations (Pearson *et al.*, 2023). Racehorses are bred for maximum speed before preservation and longevity, and are pushed to their physical and mental limits for performance - often leading to shattered legs which cannot be healed.

The on-track fatality rate of horse races in the USA is 0.5%, with the percentage rising to 2.25% for jump races such as the UK Grand National (Pearson, 2023). Due to overbreeding and the industry's inability to provide all but the best racehorses with homes after their retirement, thousands of them are sent to slaughter every year, both in the USA and the UK (RSPCA, 2025; Battuello, 2025). While horses have a lifespan of thirty years, the majority of racehorses worldwide never reach their fifth birthday.

Since the popularity of *Umamusume*, the Japanese Racing Association has seen a noticeable spike in younger adults attending racing events, placing bets, buying official racehorse merchandise, and even applying for jobs in the horse racing industry – stating that more than half of new applicants at Japanese horse racing barns were inspired by *Umamusume* (Memoroar, 2025).

Following the game's Western all-platform release on June 26, 2025, one fan from the UK loved it so much that they bought a racehorse of their own (Fisher, 2025). Cygames also directly sponsored the American Oaks and the 151st annual running of the Kentucky Derby – the largest and most-watched horse race in the USA. American fans of the game are found in *Umamasume* cosplay, attending races held in local racetracks such as the Santa Anita.

8. Conclusion

Though the trend has been positive from the early 1900s to the 2000s, there is overwhelming evidence that the representation of horses in animation and other mediums is both a consequence and reinforcer of outdated beliefs and misinformation. Discussion and reform in media representation could be a powerful way to change cultural attitudes towards horses and improve their welfare. Stories focusing on horses especially need to watch out for anthropocentric tropes such as symbolic reduction and the cooperative horse narrative. All in all, there has yet to be a horse story with as much of a positive welfare impact as *Black Beauty*.

List of Images

Fig. 1 David, J. L. (1801) *Napoleon Crossing the Alps* [Oil on Canvas]

Fig. 2 *Cinderella's Father Holding a Whip* (1950) [Film still] In: *Cinderella*. California: Walt Disney Animation Studios.

Fig. 3 *Non-Anthropomorphised Horse Waiting in the Rain* (1955) [Film still] In: *Lady and the Tramp*. California: Walt Disney Animation Studios.

Fig. 4 *Objectified Horse in Encanto* (2021) [Film still] In: *Encanto*. California: Walt Disney Animation Studios.

Fig. 5 *Phillipe and Gaston's Horse* (1991) [Film still] In: *Beauty and the Beast*. California: Walt Disney Animation Studios.

Fig. 6 *Elsa Taming the Nokk* (2021) [Film still] In: *Frozen 2*. California: Walt Disney Animation Studios.

Fig. 7 *Romanticised Depiction of Horse Ownership* (2021) [Film still] In: *Spirit Untamed*. California: DreamWorks Pictures.

Fig. 8 *Spirit Looking At His Future* (2002) [Film still] In: *Spirit: Stallion of the Cimarron*. California: DreamWorks Pictures.

Fig. 9 *Horses: Maron and Mikage Homare* (2013) [Television still] In: *Silver Spoon*. Tokyo: A-1 Pictures, Inc.

Fig. 10 *Horse in Episode 1, Centaurworld* (2021) [Television still] In: *Centaurworld*. California: Netflix Animation Studios.

Fig. 11 *Please Do Not Slap Horses* (2021) [Television still] In: *Centaurworld*. California: Netflix Animation Studios.

Fig. 12 *Umamasume: Pretty Derby Game Cover* (2021) [Game still] In: *Umamasume: Pretty Derby*. Tokyo: Cygames Inc.

List of Films/Television Shows

Black Beauty (1877)

Beauty and the Beast (1991)

Centaurworld (2021)

Cinderella (1950)

Encanto (2021)

Frozen (2013)

Frozen 2 (2021)

Lady and the Tramp (1955)

Last Unicorn, The (1982)

Little Mermaid, The (1989)

My Little Pony: Friendship is Magic (2010)

One Hundred and One Dalmatians (1961)

Princess and the Frog (2009)

Silver Spoon (2013)

Snow White (1937)

Spirit Untamed (2021)

Spirit, Stallion of the Cimarron (2002)

Tangled (2010)

Umamasume: Pretty Derby (2021)

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Appendix

Screenshot of conversation
(Friedman, 2025)

Bianca Friedman, PhD

• Mobile • 20h ago

Myra Sethi (She/Her) • 11:31 AM

I'm curious, did you watch and/or consider the [2001](#) film Spirit: The Stallion of the Cimarron for your thesis?

Though it is animated and your thesis seems focused on live-action films, I think it's a great counter-example to the other Wild Horse films you mentioned in your essay - as it actually rewards the protagonist for resisting domestication and lacks the cooperative horse/perfect-match anthropocentric narrative present in the other examples.

It's not perfect, but I would consider it to be the least anthropocentric-narrative horse movie I've seen so far.

Bianca Friedman, PhD (She/Her) • 4:01 PM

Hi Myra, thanks for your messages and the interesting comment you made.

My thesis considers live-actions only, so this is why I haven't included it in my corpus, even though it was in my proposal at the very early stages. Spirit is a very interesting example. In my opinion, what you say is true (he is free at the end of the film), but I guess there is another aspect to consider. In the representation he resists, throwing all white cowboys to the ground and then running away. However, he IS SET free, after accepting the other outcast of the film (the Native American who is imprisoned just like him), he doesn't really free himself via his own ability to resist domestication: he just accepts a kinder form of domestication. It's quite annoying, but there seems to be an overly present human counterpart that entitles the horse to (re)gain freedom on the basis of X (merit? Achievements? Affinity? Other anthropocentric justifications?). A similar example is "Hidalgo", who is (again) set free after winning the impossible race in the desert.